

**EDUCATIONAL SIGNIFICANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL VIEWS OF
ENCYCLOPEDIA SCIENTISTS**

Abdurakhimov Shoqosim

Karshi State Pedagogical Institute

ANNOTATION

The article highlights the work of great scientists, authors of encyclopedic works on education, the role of ideas and views in the world and their contribution to the development of pedagogical ideas, as well as their importance in modern practice.

Key words: scientists-encyclopedias, education, upbringing, man, perfection pedagogy, education and training.

INTRODUCTION

Education influenced the development of a person intellectually and morally, and the formation of a person, in turn, helped the development of a society. So, the process of ensuring the development of a person with the ability to think and the social development of society are formed in a mutual relationship. Knowing the nature of this historical process tells us that human thinking has been formed for a long time and in complex conditions. We rely on the creative legacy of great writers and scholars as the main source for studying our cultural wealth in the historical process. Especially during the period of Eastern renaissance, pure pedagogical works were created, and the scientific creations of educational scientists, who left a name with their immortal teaching about the special and general methods of human development in education, retain their value to this day. The ideas and views of lexicographers on education have also impressed European scientists. In fact, our great ancestors like Muhammad Khorazmi Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Raikhan Beruni Abu Ali ibn Sina, Mahmud Zamakhshari, Alisher Navai conquered the highest heights of world science with their scientific and creative heritage. In this regard, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said in his speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the Day of Teachers and Trainers on October 1: "If we look at history, we see that our motherland, located at the intersection of the Great Silk Road, has been one of the centers of high civilization and culture since ancient times. . The rich scientific and cultural heritage of our people, ancient stone inscriptions, priceless architectural monuments, rare manuscripts, and various antiques testify to the deep roots of our statehood history of three thousand years.

The teachings of the "Holy Qur'an" and "Hadith" form the basis of the views of the great Eastern thinkers of that time on education and upbringing. They express their views on the basis of the moral standards necessary for the education of young people, their own life experience, Islamic ethics, the requirements of the Qur'an and Hadiths, and on this basis, the actions that young people should constantly follow. describes the sequence and systematic order of moral standards. The fruitful creative products of those great breeds were able to be programmed in the education of the young generation today. The great encyclopedist Abu Nasr Farabi, who made an incomparable contribution to the organization of the educational process with his teachings and directions, emphasizes the following in this regard: - "Education is the unification of theoretical virtues between peoples and townspeople, and education is the unification of innate virtues and practical professional qualities among these peoples"; - "In order for the educational process to be successful, the educator must be educated"; - "Education is carried out only by words and learning, and education by practical work and experience"; - "Education is the teaching of the practical skills of every people, nation, work - action, profession - craft"; - "Man is the most perfect and mature end of world development." The great thinker and encyclopedist, Abu Nasr Farabi, through these thoughts, expressed valuable information about the need for education and upbringing in the development of the personality, the main goal expected from the educational methods and the methods of education in child education, and the child from birth to standing on his feet. It was mentioned that great attention is paid to being brought up in a certain order.

CONCLUSION

The rich cultural and educational heritage of the Great Eastern thinkers always calls the young generation to honest work, courage and generosity, humility and justice, and kindness and consequence. The spirituality, history, unique customs and traditions of any nation or nation cannot be imagined without national values. The attention to the issue of education and upbringing is reflected in the works of Eastern scholars, including the wisdom of Abu Rayhan Beruni, "Nightmare" by Kaikovus, "Mahbub ul-Qulub" by Alisher Navoi, "Ethics of Muhsini" by Husayn Vaiz Koshifi. . In the mentioned works, it is a metaphor that if a child is the happiness of parents, education is the child's today, tomorrow and future. As the thinker Ibn Sina said to educators, "Whatever advice you give to someone, first of all follow it yourself", in the education of children, in expanding and enriching their spiritual worldview, the opinions, advices and wisdom of thinkers it is the duty of all of us to follow and use them.

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